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Challenges of Modular Learning Modality to Grade V Learners in Relation to their Academic Performance

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Abstract

The purpose of the study was to determine the challenges of grade five learners, also aimed to examine the relationship between the challenges of grade five learners to their academic performance using modular learning modality. Sixty Learners from the six sections of grade five of Balo-i Central Elementary School were chosen as the respondent of the study, convenient sampling technique was used. Data were drawn from the survey questionnaire and assessment tools. Statistical tools using Weighted Mean and Standard deviation was used to describe the respondent's level of challenges to Grade 5 learners in using modular learning and Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used to determine the significant relationship between the level of challenges to Grade 5 learners in modular learning modality and their academic performance. Result of the study revealed that there is a significant relationship between the challenges encountered by the grade V pupils to their academic performance. Furthermore, challenges encountered by the grade V pupils did affect their academic performance. Thus, the study inferred that the respondents' level of challenges encountered using modular learning modality play significant to their academic performance. Hence, it is hereby recommended that the proposed orientation program be implemented.

Keywords: *challenges, modular learning, academic performance, descriptive-correlational research design*

Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic is the largest disruption in history in all aspects of human lives. It has affected several millions of people especially in their educational systems worldwide. Most governments around the world have temporarily closed educational institutions in an attempt to reduce the spread of COVID-19 and no one knows when this pandemic will end. Every country is now currently implementing policy guidelines and protocols on how to avert the said virus because of the rising numbers of infected people. Community quarantines and lockdowns led the learners to study at home in response to school closures. UNESCO recommended the use of distance learning programmes and open educational applications and platforms that schools and teachers can use to reach learners remotely and limit the disruption of education. However, imposing these programs has shed problems to the learners with regard to their quality of learning.

Modular learning is an Alternative Delivery Mode (ADM) of education in this new normal. Based on the survey conducted by DepEd on school opening, it is the most preferred learning delivery by parents for their children this school year. However, only some were not in favor, because the use of this ADM would only be convenient for those who have educated parents, siblings or anyone in the family who can assist them well. What about those who do not have anyone in the family who can assist? Learners without proper assistance in learning at home will have a hard time to study. Another concern of the parents is the time that will be spent in teaching their children. Some don't have time because as we all know, they work for their daily living and that lead them to neglect their responsibility in teaching their children.

With this concern, Gonzales (2020) state that schools' stakeholders are the most affected during this time of pandemic. They are mostly the ones at a loss and are the ones sacrificing, may it be either academically, financially, or both. According to the Secretary of Education Leonor M. Briones, distance learning will be a major component of learning delivery for the incoming school year. The physical opening of schools will depend on the risk severity grading or classification of a locality, pursuant to guidelines of the Department of Health or Inter-Agency Task Force on Emerging Infectious Diseases (IATF-EID).

DepEd Order No. 45 series 2002, strongly mandates from the main thrusts of the 2002 basic education curriculum policy that every child is a reader at the beginning of the school year. Reading is a first guide to an effective teaching to boost a learner to read well by the end of third grade, ensuring that all learners advance later to grades well prepared to achieve their full academic potential (Gulas, 2010). However, too many learners in schools across the Philippines and other countries are having a difficult time with Learners performance in reading. Elements of teamwork have explained improvements in programs of family improvement. Andrews (2018) found that research on children's literacy development provides overwhelming evidence of the connections between literacy resources at home and children's literacy development. Generally learners struggling reading who enter the school learning from their daily reading activities the year in first grade level. Therefore, learners will have a cost of early failure in reading is exceptional high in basic reading instruction (Jagtap, 2018).

On the other hand, Medical News Today (2020), believe that corona virus is spreading exponentially and many countries locked their education system, and enforcing strict quarantine to their people to control the spread of this highly contagious disease. The government's focus on fulfilling equipment, organizing medical institutions, and laboratory centers, identification of the virus, training health workers, and creating awareness for their people (Haleem et al., 2020). Education has been the pillar of development of every

country, so education is principal to the development and growth of all countries. The education system has been affected by several challenges ranging from changes in the education curriculum to closing down the education system due to widespread pandemic diseases (Owusu-Fordjour et al., 2015).

UNESCO (2020) reports that 87% of the world's student population is affected by COVID-19 due to school closures. UNESCO is launching distance learning practices and reaching students who are most at risk are inevitable. Over 1.5 billion students in 195 countries are affected by COVID-19 due to pandemic school closures. In Niranjana (2020) report, he studied that COVID-19 impacted not only the overall economy and our day to day life, but also emotional, mental, and physical health, also, losses in national and international business, poor cash flow in the market, locked national and international travelling; moreover, disruption of the celebration of cultural, and festive events, stress among the population, the closures of hotels, restaurants, religious, and entertainment places (Evans, 2020).

The purpose of this study was to determine the challenges of intermediate pupils specifically Grade V learners in Balo-i Central Elementary School of modular learning modality. It also aimed to examine the relationship between the challenges of Grade V pupils to their academic performance using modular learning modality. The study was conducted on the First Grading of SY 2021-2022.

With the findings in this study, the researcher was hopeful to determine the level of their challenges in order to make adjustments and coping mechanisms for the effects to diverse learners by making use of varied teaching pedagogy that would fit to the needs of the learners.

Research Questions

The main thrust of this study was to determine the challenges on modular learning modality to Grade V learners in relation to their academic performance at Balo-i Central Elementary School. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the levels of challenges of modular learning modality to Grade V learners in relation to academic performance in terms of:
 - 1.1. concentration factor on Modular Learning;
 - 1.2. student struggles with self-studying;
 - 1.3. time consumed in answering the modules;
 - 1.4. learning environment;
 - 1.5. mental support; and
 - 1.6. academic assistance at home?
2. What is the academic performance of Grade V pupils using modular learning modality?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the challenges to Grade V pupils using modular learning modality to their academic performance?
4. What possible orientation program on modular learning can be proposed based on the findings of the study?

Methodology

Research Design

The study used the descriptive-correlational research design to describe the data about the population that was studied. It described the challenges of modular learning to Grade V pupils such as their concentration factor, student struggles with self-studying, time consumed in answering the modules, their learning environment, mental support and assistance at home.

Moreover, correlation method was used to test the relationship between two or more variables existed, as this study investigated the relationship between challenges of modular learning modality Grade V pupils to their academic performance.

Respondents

The respondents of this study were the ten selected learners from each section of Grade V of Balo-i Central Elementary School. A total of 60 learners were chosen from the six sections of Grade V as respondents of the study. Since it is hard to reach students because of pandemic, convenient sampling technique was used in this study to identify the number of desired character that suit the purpose of the study being conducted.

Instruments

In this study, the researcher-made questionnaire was used as instrument. This was refined with the guidance of the thesis adviser and experts from the Division office. After corrections were made, this was pilot tested in the nearest school which is Mumungan Elementary School.

The questionnaire consisted of two parts. Part I contained the questionnaire on respondent's challenges in modular learning in terms of concentration factor on modular learning, student struggles with self-studying, time consumed in answering the modules, learning environment, mental support, and academic assistance at home. These components were described by its level through a Likert scale rated as 4- strongly agree; 3- agree; 2- disagree and 1- strongly disagree. Part II is the average rating of students for First Quarter SY

2020-2021.

Procedure

The researcher was the one who visited the school in conducting the study. To facilitate the gathering of the data, the researcher asked permission from the School Principal of Balo-i, Central Elementary School with the letter signed and approved by the research adviser in order to conduct the study.

During the gathering of data, parents of the respondents who were getting the modules were asked to allow the researcher to have their child as a respondent of the study. They were assured that the information given by the learners will be kept with outmost confidentiality. After that, Parents were given instructions and oriented on how the learner answer the questionnaire, after that, questionnaires were distributed to the parents for their child to answer. They were told that the questionnaire will be collected on the day of retrieval of module and a clear direction in answering the questions were given relevant to the study at hand.

The researcher then requested the School Guidance Counselor through a letter request to the School Principal for the copy of the average rating of the respondents for First Quarter. They gave the rating of the chosen respondents in random order to preserve the identity of the owner.

Data Analysis

The data were tabulated and interpreted in acquiring the actual information needed. The following statistical techniques was used in answering the different problems presented.

For Problem 1 and 2, Weighted Mean and Standard deviation were used to describe the respondent's level of challenges to Grade 5 learners in using modular learning modality in terms of learners in relation to academic performance in terms of concentration factor on modular learning, student struggles with self-studying, time consumed in answering the modules, learning environment, mental support, and academic assistance at home.

For problem 3, Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used to determine the significant relationship between the level of challenges to Grade 5 learners in modular learning modality and their academic performance.

All the computation was done manually with the statistics software of an accredited statistician.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the data gathered and the analyses as well as the interpretation of data. The answers are presented based on the sequence as presented in Chapter 1.

Problem 1: What are the challenges of Grade V learners using modular learning modality in terms of: concentration factor on modular learning, student struggles with self-studying, time consumed in answering the modules, learning environment, mental support, and academic assistance at home?

Table 1. *Challenges Encountered in terms of Concentration Factor on Modular Learning*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Qualitative Description</i>
1. I get distracted whenever I answer my modules.	3.62	0.49	Strongly Agree
2. I have found the modules confusing to work on.	3.52	0.57	Strongly Agree
3. I have found the modules uninteresting to work on.	3.45	0.57	Strongly Agree
4. I can't focus answering my modules at home especially when the Television is on.	3.59	0.50	Strongly Agree
5. I easily shift my attention to other things like playing gadgets and etc. whenever I answer my modules	3.28	0.65	Strongly Agree
Over-all Mean	3.49	0.56	Strongly Agree

Table 1 presents the mean, standard deviation, description and interpretation of the Grade five learners using modular learning modality in their concentration factor on modular learning based on challenges encountered.

Results displayed on table 1 indicate that the overall mean shows the description of the learner's challenges skills in terms of the concentration factor on modular learning was to a "strongly agree" ($\bar{X}=3.492$, $SD=0.558$). This signifies that the level of Challenges encountered by the learners was "very important". This means that it helped the learners to reflect on the relevance of learning at home with hindrances for coping to improve quality learning in modular learning modality. This finding is supported of the study conducted by Nichols Crowe (2015) that education pacing biggest challenges of today's managing capability that meet quality learning through training possesses quality learning materials and other learning enhancement. Moreover, wide variety of learning materials that cater a broad range of needs for different grade level could cater also by creating a mini library to satisfy the pupils learning needs.

The table also discloses that highest indicator mean shows that the highest indicator mean shows that "strongly agree". This means that the level of Challenges encountered by the learners was very important. The result also shows Modular Learning Modality in terms of Concentration Factor on Modular Learning with the knowledge of the school head, teachers, and parents for the learners. During the

implementation of modules some of the pupils get distracted whenever they answer the modules, still the parents were encouraging the pupils ensuring the progress of the mastery of the lesson in accordance to the k-12 curriculum.

According to Folsom (2020), a numerous trained pre-school teacher had focus on the best practices for distance learning in response to COVID 19. The evident of pacing the pandemic over our education had suffered time frame, quality bonding with the teachers, parent's collaboration in the school, and learner's socialization which supposedly align for more learning enhancement. Also, the researcher had an opportunity to talk to one of the respondent, he mentioned that; "Concentration factor of modular learning is an important learning focus that reiterated by our parents that simply imply the quality of time management. This was one of our challenges to overcome that attested by the parent's facilitated learners learning at home in which there were learning barriers makes the learners unfocused to their learning, most of the learners were a child labour with their own risk."

The concentration factor develops and implements a successful modular learning environment which is an essential hindrance to the concentration of pupils learning with wide variety of effective learning materials Nichols Crowe (2015).

It can be gleaned also in table 1 the lowest indicator mean shows that "strongly agree". The learners pacify easily to shift an attention to other things like playing gadgets and others whenever answering the modules. It implies that the level of Challenges encountered by the pupils is very important. Parents were responsible on the academic performance of the learners in their respective houses in the sense that learning approaches weighing learning environmental care.

The study Mulwa (2015) supports the concepts of learning responsibility of teacher is required to know what the learner needs in order to learn new concepts. A child is ready for a new concept but it inculcated the struggle when all the sub-concepts intruded with gadgets that are support to learn through a prerequisite to the concept are being mastered supposedly. Mulwa (2015) added that learning through gadgets do not have learning if and only if parent have proper guidance on the learning of the learners at home.

Table 2 presents the mean values and standard deviation of the level of challenges encountered of grade five learners on the skills of student struggle with self-studying.

Table 2. Challenges Encountered in terms of learner's Struggle with Self-Studying on Modular Learning

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Qualitative Description</i>
1. I have difficulty in understanding the lessons written in the modules.	3.34	0.61	Strongly Agree
2. I'm having a hard time in answering my modules.	3.31	0.60	Strongly Agree
3. The workload of these modules is too heavy for me to study.	3.52	0.57	Strongly Agree
4. I can't easily understand the lesson written in the module because I have no one where to ask about the lesson.	3.34	0.67	Strongly Agree
5. My modules have weaned my enthusiasm for learning.	3.48	0.63	Strongly Agree
Over-all Mean	3.40	0.62	Strongly Agree

Data on table 2 shows that respondents answered, "Strongly Agree" ($\bar{X}=3.398$, $SD=0.619$) in terms of learners struggle with self-studying. The overall result for these challenges skills, implies that learners struggle with self-studying and could not easily understood the lesson specified in the module. However, looking forward about the struggle felt by the learners are "very important", no one where to ask about the lesson except their parents who needed to educate on the process on giving instructions. These challenges encountered by the learners during the distribution of modules through their parents have enlightened the struggles.

One of the parents said that "Our struggle is also the struggle of our child specially in self-studying using modules are the primary concern that lessons during face to face instruction are somewhat we really needed in our everyday lessons. Lessons reflected in the modules needs thorough explanation by the teachers in which our child and us parents cannot give us the proper instruction because we need also to be educated same us what we expected."

Parents are now aware on the use of modules as the routine and same procedure with different lessons and other pupils tends not to answer but return the modules without answer. However, pupils are not urging to answer the modules with their parents and other activities sometimes because of the pandemic. In the sense that parents are given instructions so the pupils are encouraged to pursue their schooling. The appropriate strategy in most countries is to use all possible delivery modes with the infrastructure that exists today. Most teachers use modular or online tools to assure that lesson plans, videos, tutorials, and other resources are available for some students and probably, the pupils have convenient to answer the module.

However, the readymade modules led teachers to rely on the capability of the pupils to read and answer comprehensively. Moreover, Angara (2020) says that, as for the case of improving the eagerness of the pupils to read and understand comprehensively. We have to call on and support an integral resource for the family: the parents. Indeed, parents and guardians must be empowered to help the learning process of the pupils.

Table 2 shows the highest indicator mean indicates "strongly agree". It implies that the level of challenges encountered by the pupils is very important. Learners are coming from different parts of the Barangay Balo-i Lanao del Norte that needs learning management and instruction. The workload of these modules is too heavy for me to study. Hence, the study of Angara (2020) supports the importance of modules in accordance to the learning support of the learners through parent's participation in their respective houses. It means that

challenges occurs using the modular learning modality as part of the success of modules concerned.

It can also be gleaned in the table that the lowest indicator mean signified “strongly Agree” on the how they pointed out the hard time of answering the modules. This would mean that the level of Challenges encountered by the learners is very important. It is very important in the sense that the struggle of parent’s and learners at home will be sorting some important resiliencies to give some remediation in accordance to invoke solution on the development of the learning situation of the learners. Moreover, Toquero (2020) said that education in pandemic traces the bounty of struggle of parents and the learners that sometimes tend not to enroll for schooling to the next grade level. Discouragement occurs when modules were distributed, parents are longing that face-to-face classes will be resumed. Meaning modular learning modality had a great impact to the parents; first they do not know how to explain to their children the main object of the lesson; second, they were learning the teacher’s instruction guiding lessons; third, parents are guided on what to do particularly in the coastal school; lastly, both parents and learners have a collaborative learning principle during pandemic.

Table 3 revealed that in another level of challenges, “time consume in answering the modules”, pupils on these challenges answered, “Strongly Agree” (\bar{x} =3.456, SD =0.601). Generally, the levels of challenges of grade V pupils on modules are not finish in a given time. These areas of challenges are very important to oversee in answering the modules in an exact time.

Moreover, Saavedra (2020) stressed that as a pupils should be considered the crisis education, learners’ learning at home losses interest in school rather than having gone to work with their parents in a particular establishment or in the farm and increases dropout. Moreover, the educational services quite long the implementation and also the process due to the constraint of the pandemic health protocol.

Table 3. Challenges Encountered using Modular Learning Modality in terms of Time Consume in Answering the Modules

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Qualitative Description</i>
1. I have lack of sleep due to many activities that I have to do within a week.	3.59	0.63	Strongly Agree
2. The time given to us to answer our modules is not enough.	3.59	0.50	Strongly Agree
3. I can’t finish answering my modules within the time given to us.	3.62	0.56	Strongly Agree
4. The time given to answer my modules is not enough because of the household chores that I have to do at home.	3.31	0.60	Strongly Agree
5. I always cannot pass my other modules on time because I don’t have enough time in answering it.	3.17	0.71	Agree
Over-all Mean	3.46	0.60	Strongly Agree

Adding to this learner who struggled to answer completely the modules and some parents are initiating to answer the modules of their child. As observed in the distribution of modules, parents are sharing of ideas on how to answer the modules and possible answer in each question. Angara (2020), supported the ideas that parents and guardians must be empowered to help the learning process of the pupils as set of routine that integrate time for studies and education through modular learning.

As shown in the table, the highest indicator mean (\bar{x} =3.62) indicate “strongly agree”. It implies that the level of Challenges encountered by the pupils is very important. Pupils were given emphasis in answering the modules that they could not cope with the given time. Learning is art of emulsifying knowledge that has to undertake self-management according to (Folsom, 2020). Haleem (2020), supported the study of Folsom that learners were struggled in answering the modules; modules are distributed without instruction coming from the teachers that needs further instructions for clear understanding particularly English, Mathematics, and Science.

Furthermore, the lowest indicator mean (\bar{x} =3.17) indicates “agree”. It implies that the level of challenges encountered by the pupils are important; modules are time consuming that some of the pupils cannot answer the specified time for a particular modules and they missed to submit on time and some were unattended to answer the modules. This is supported from the study of Ambayon (2020) that learner’s achievement matters of the teaching performance of the teacher. This could be deemed on the output performance of the learners in answering the modules.

The results reflected in Table 4 shows that the learners on this kind of challenges answered, “Strongly agree”, (\bar{X} =3.296, SD =0.691). Respondents on this level of challenges encountered have knowledge on how the learning environment must be placed in an area found inside their respective houses. Learning environment is the contemporary learning workplace at home which maximizes enough space to keeps learning study habits comfortably. It implies that it is very important that we know study room is not only refers to school classroom, library but it is how being comfortable in a particular place, even if under the tree as long as comfort learning with ability to maximize the learning environment.

The quality of the Home Learning Environment is a key forecaster of a child's early developmental language and ability in the future success; positive experiences can have lasting and life changing impacts. Early language ability is consistently linked to later outcomes including school attainment and job prospects (Toquero, 2020). Parents as the learning facilitator are doing best on the quality learning inputs to their respective children. Unlike before the pandemic, parents are entrusted the quality time of teachers dealing with their children.

The highest indicator mean (\bar{x} =3.48) indicates “strongly agree”. It implies that the levels of challenges encountered by the learners are very important. The learning environment of the learners signifies that affect their performance due to have noisy surrounding in which learners are unfocused in their study. According to Toquero (2020) learning environment are important on the study performance of

the learners, the habitual of learners in learning strategy would help enough to have solemn and having strategic learning environment.

Table 4. *Challenges Encountered using Modular Learning Modality in terms of Learning Environment*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Qualitative Description</i>
1. I don't have a study room where I can answer and study my modules quietly.	3.45	0.69	Strongly Agree
2. I study in a poorly-ventilated area at home.	3.28	0.70	Strongly Agree
3. I have a noisy surrounding that's why I can't focus in my study.	3.10	0.62	Agree
4. I don't have enough things to use like books, dictionaries and gadgets that will help me in studying.	3.17	0.71	Agree
15. I don't have enough space in our house that keeps me to study comfortably.	3.48	0.74	Strongly Agree
Over-all Mean	3.30	0.69	Strongly Agree

The lowest indicator mean ($\bar{x}=3.10$) state that "I have a noisy surrounding that's why I can't focus my study". It implies that the levels of challenges encountered by the learners are rarely important. Learners' learning environment in this aspect makes support of improving the performance in its study habit so that the level of challenges encountered could be pacify to a better learning environment. The performance of (Hindi & Paratore, 2007) vouched that the learning integrity of having appraised learning environment gives more prudent and quantifiable structuring of learning environment.

Table 5 presents the mean values and standard deviation of the level of challenges encountered of grade V pupils on the skills of Mental Support.

Data on table 5 shows that respondents answered, "Strongly Agree" ($\bar{X}=3.262$ $SD=0.628$) in terms of Mental Support. The overall result for these challenges skills, implies that Mental Support are feeling of motivation when doing my modules because of lack of support. It is a coping mechanism of the performance of pupils. However, looking forward about the support of parents is very important, nobody can motivate and emotion doing the modules alone or with the support of parents who are learning also the modules by updating education.

Table 5. *Challenges Encountered using Modular Learning Modality in terms of Mental Support*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Qualitative Description</i>
1 My parents does not cheer me up whenever I'm having a hard time in my modules.	3.21	0.62	Agree
2. I don't have anybody who can help me in coping up every time I feel stressed.	3.34	0.55	Strongly Agree
3. I feel like giving up because no one motivates me whenever I feel stressed and lonely.	3.24	0.74	Agree
4 Nobody at home understands me whenever I vent my emotions with regards on doing my modules.	3.24	0.64	Agree
5 I don't feel motivated when doing my modules because of lack of support from my family	3.28	0.59	Strongly Agree
Over-all Mean	3.26	0.63	Strongly Agree

The level of challenges of the pupils also affects the mental performance of the parents in terms of their workmanship for their family. However, some parents does not participate the learning modality of their child (Hines, 2011). The engagement of learning being revealed that parents are needs to educate, which stimulate the pupils and build curiosity in accomplishing the module requirements.

As we can gleaned in table 5, the highest indicator mean ($\bar{X}=3.34$) indicate that "Strongly Agree"). This implies that the levels of challenges encountered by the pupils are very important. The Mental support of the learners does not have anybody who can help in coping up every time they felt stressed. Hines (2011) stresses that the mental development of the learners. This means that mental support of the learners matter most on the family back grounds and the learning environment in the school as well as in their respective family back ground

The lowest indicator mean. ($\bar{X}=3.21$) indicates "agree". This implies that the levels of challenges encountered by the pupils are important. It shows that a parent doesn't cheer the learners whenever having hard time to in answering the modules. It seems that their respective parents do not have enough educational background or the grade level of parents undertake on their educational background. The study of Nicholas (2015), justified the importance of mental preparation of the learners. This means that collaborative of learning instruction would enhance the learning performance through their mental skills support to each learning inhabitant.

Table 6 presents the mean values and standard deviation of the level of challenges encountered of grade V pupils on the skills of academic assistance at home.

Table 6 revealed the data that respondents answered, "Strongly Agree" ($\bar{X}=3.324$ $SD=0.740$) in terms of Academic Assistance at Home. The overall result for these challenges skills, implies that the levels of challenges encountered by the pupils are very important. It means that the academic Assistance at Home would always seek assistance to answer the modules, parents were not able to help and assist their child because they were busy from their respective work. However, the respondents had the hard time to answer the module and their parents were looking forward on the support of teachers to give systematic instructional approaches; nobody can help and guide them in the process of assessing quality result of the modules.

Table 6. *Challenges Encountered using Modular Learning Modality in terms of Academic Assistance at Home*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Qualitative Description</i>
1. I don't have someone to help me whenever I'm having a hard time answering my modules.	3.24	0.69	Agree
2. I don't have anybody to teach and guide me in answering my modules.	3.14	0.74	Agree
3. I only have myself in answering my modules because no one in our home is able to read and write.	3.31	0.79	Agree
4 No one in our house is able to help and assist me in answering my modules because they are busy in our daily living (work).	3.45	0.74	Strongly Agree
5 Nobody at home helps me whenever I seek assistance to answer my modules.	3.48	0.74	Strongly Agree
Over-all Mean	3.32	0.74	Agree

According to Nicholas (2015), the modular learning has integrated long before that the long-distance learning must have to undergo modular learning approach with varied integration of values that the learners as assistance from their parents for further understanding of the learning module. Meaning the quality of learning does it involve challenges but with the bottomless support of the parents, the academic goals were achieved.

As shown in the table the highest indication mean ($\bar{X}=3.48$) in terms of academic assistance at home indicates "strongly agree". The learning on this challenges skills using the modular learning modality signifies that nobody at home helps me whenever I seek assistance to answer my modules. It implies that the levels of challenges encountered by the pupils are very important. This means that parents are trusted to their children in answering the modules. Both parents are working and they do not have time for learning assistance and other parents are not capable enough to give instruction to give instruction because they have to learn also on the learning situation of their children.

Academic assistance at home were given illustrative encouragement of the pupils like accomplishing the modules. Parents were very diligent in helping the pupils and gave instructions on how to answer the activities to those professional parents but some parents need to learn because of what they had acquired and some have gained elementary level only.

According to Cristobal (2020), modular approach is an inimitable way of teaching so the teachers should be provided adequate training about how to strategize and implement a module in classroom setting. Its instruction is more operatively in teaching learning method as parents' involvement in an instructional facilitation at home.

Problem 2: What is the academic performance of Grade V pupils using modular learning modality?

Table 7 shows the summary of the academic performance of pupils by subject. It was noted that 2 subjects rated as "Very Satisfactory" and six (6) rated as "Satisfactory". This means that the level of academic performance as presented in the table with the weighted point average fall under the "satisfactory" category. The standard deviation shows that the responses of the participants were dispersed. This means that the academic performance of the pupils vary on the challenges encountered by the grade 5 pupils. This enhanced learning capabilities of the pupils in their respective houses.

Table 7. *Academic Performance of Grade V Pupils using Modular Learning Modality*

<i>Subjects</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Qualitative Description</i>
English	79.36	2.36	Satisfactory
Mathematics	80.12	3.21	Satisfactory
Science	81.43	3.26	Satisfactory
Filipino	77.92	2.01	Satisfactory
Araling Panlipunan	83.24	3.49	Satisfactory
Edukasyon sa Pagpapahalaga	85.34	3.62	Very Satisfactory
MAPEH	83.17	3.38	Satisfactory
HEKASI/TLE	86.72	3.72	Very Satisfactory
Overall Average	80.65	2.01	Satisfactory

The overall mean results ($\bar{X}=82.16$, $SD=3.14$) of the academic performance of grade 5 pupils using modular learning modality implies that mostly of the pupils answered "satisfactory". Thus, the academic performance having threaten when pandemic strikes which affect every pupil and parent as the learning facilitator at home. The task of the teachers before pandemic is the degree of learning in which pupils has gained a particular grade or mark my teacher.

It is the performance rating of student based on the implementing guidelines on the performance based on grading System (DepEd order no. 8, s. 2016. Performance of the students varies on the aspect of self-gaining principles that to sustain the quality learning gained during the pandemic. Hence, learning of the student are limited in the sense that no perfect instructional guide by the parents rather than instruction of the teacher inside the classroom instruction in the school.

Apiong (2020), claimed that parents play an important role and considerable role in the development of their children's attitudes towards the new normal education that taken care the pupils challenges during the pandemic. The roles of the parents are giving instruction to quality learning instructions during and post evaluation of the modules. The instructional guides of the parents are limited.

They need also to quantify the learning capability of the parents by giving the instructions to their respective children learning at home. Further, Folsom (2020) stresses that the performance of the learners in effect of the pandemic distance learning had gained more on struggle of the learners as parents also felt difficult on how they impact quality instruction to their children, the fact that they need also to learned on what their children learning as they read and answer that modules in each subject from their teacher in school. Folsom added that children attitudes in support to the study of Apiong (2020) in answering the module dealing a discouragement because most of them do not understand how it being stresses the learning particularly Mathematics, English and Science subjects.

Problem 3: Is there a significant relationship between the challenges encountered of Grade V pupils to their academic performance using modular learning modality?

Table 8. *Analysis on The Relationship between the Challenges Encountered of Grade V Pupils to their Academic Performance using Modular Learning Modality*

<i>Independent Variable</i>	<i>Dependent Variable</i>	<i>Correlation Coefficient</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Remarks</i>
Challenges Encountered by the Grade V Pupils	Academic Performance	0.330	0.040	Significant

**Correlation is Significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)*

Table 8 presents the relationship between the Challenges encountered by Grade V pupils in their academic performance using modular learning modality. It showed that the null hypothesis tested 0.05 level of significance is not rejected. As shown in the table, the computed p-value was (0.037) and showed significant relationship between the challenges encountered of grade V pupils to their academic performance using the modular learning modality. In other words it meant that challenges encountered by the grade V pupils did affect the academic performance. This could be due to the fact that the Modular Learning Modality pertained the new normal education where highly involved.

While was believed that from the start of the implementation of Modular learning Modality this could lead to the deterioration of the academic performance of the grade V pupils, this was negated by this particular study showing that there is a significant relationship that existed between the two variable on the challenges encountered by the grade V pupils to their academic performance using the modular learning modality has an impact to a need of leaning management guidance on the development of the learning skills as indicated in the modules..

Moreover, these results agree with the findings of Apiong (2020) stating that pupils who performed well academically have some advantages. Academic performance serves as a key criterion in order to judge pupils true potentials and capabilities. Identifying these potential capabilities are necessary to better hone them. It is one on the determinant of success in life particularly; we are facing with the COVID-19 pandemic.

The findings also complemented with Abao's (2017) ideas that the academic performance in the implementation K to 12 curriculum in the assessment of the learning modality encountered difficulties and may result to a positive and value-oriented situation continuing to a whole-rounded personality in the next generation. Hence, curriculum assessment on the teacher matter most on how they deliberate and assess instruction to the parent when the received the modules for the continuing learning instruction of the learners and the parents as well. Most of the teachers encourages the parents to enrol to their respect adviser to where the level of educational attainment since they are also learning during children answering the modules accompanied by their parents.

This is also supported the (DepEd Order no. 018, s. 2020) rationale starting that implementation of the basic education Learning continuity plan (BE-LCP) where tried to establish the policy guidelines of BE-LCP. It is perceived that the Challenges encountered by the grade V pupils stimulate the improvement of their performance with high incidence of cognition. Further, the result of the study indicates that there is a significant relationship between the challenges encountered by the grade V pupils to their academic performance of the pupils at 0.05 level. This means that the pupils developed and practice the higher ordered thinking skills in all learning areas. The challenges encountered by the grade V pupils to their academic performance using the modular learning modality have a significant relationship. This study may assist to improve the quality time of the pupils and strengthen the integration of values to the performance of the pupils

Conclusions

Based on the analyses and findings of the study, the following conclusions are stated below:

There is a significant relationship between the challenges encountered by the grade V pupils to their academic performance, it was proven that the challenges encountered by the grade V pupils to their academic performance using the modular learning modality have a significant relationship

Furthermore, challenges encountered by the grade V pupils did affect their academic performance. Thus, the study inferred that the respondents' level of challenges encountered using modular learning modality play significant to their academic performance.

Based on the results of the study, the researcher recommends the following:

Modular Learning Modality as an alternative delivery mode of education in this pandemic time. It is recommended that teachers and

parents should have varied strategies in teaching the learners, also giving their full support and guidance in teaching the learners to learn well is also recommended.

It is essential to give mental support to our learners in this pandemic time, Therefore, it is recommended to organize orientation program on Varied Teaching Pedagogy for Teachers and Mental Health support for parents.

Future Study may include the support of DepEd in organizing a program on Varied Teaching Pedagogy and LGU's in implementing the proposed program in the community about Mental Health.

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